

Application of Stochastic Simulation Techniques in the Analysis of a Biodiesel Production Plant

D. M. O. Silva, F. L. P. Pessoa, A. L. H. Costa

Abstract—The use of the simulation results can be limited due to the uncertainties associated with the input variables and parameters of the actual process. In this context, the main objective of this study was the use of stochastic optimization techniques in the analysis of a biodiesel production process in relation to the uncertainties involved. The stochastic simulation procedures were applied associated with Hysys process simulator. The characterization of the system behavior before the uncertainties was performed using a set of simulations, where in each, the values of one or more input variables/parameters were randomly chosen according to an appropriate probability density function. The studied cases were: the disturbance of the vacuum system pressure drop in the purification step and the influence of changes in the molar ratio of the reactants on the yield of the reaction. In conclusion it could be seen that the stochastic analysis helped to choose the best simulation tracks to the input variables/parameters studied, since it helps to know the probabilities of the proposed conditions do not meet specifications.

Keywords—Biodiesel, stochastic, thermodynamic, transesterification.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE procedure of process simulation consists in the resolution of the set of mathematical relations that describe system behavior, e.g. mass and energy balances, phase equilibrium equations, physical property calculations, etc. The mathematical model contains input variables, process parameters and output variables, as well as mathematical relations. The traditional simulation approach involves definition of input variables and process parameters; thus, output variables are evaluated by use of the model. However, utilization of the simulation results can be limited due to the uncertainties associated with the variables and parameters in the real process. The solution of the model can be significantly different from the real process response. The usual analysis of uncertainties by a sensitivity study has several drawbacks: it presents possible process scenarios but does not indicate how probable they are, the results are hard to interpret when the number of variables is large and it is difficult to identify the interactions between different variables [1].

An alternative tool for uncertainty analysis employs the concept of stochastic simulation [2]. This approach is based on a large number of simulation runs; in each run, input variables and process parameters are randomly selected according to adequate probability density functions. The set of output

variables evaluated gives important information about the behavior of the statistical process, indicating the most probable variable ranges. This analysis can be found in the literature, for example, in a study of the inaccuracies of thermodynamic evaluations in a liquefied natural gas plant [3].

II. BIODIESEL PRODUCTION

At first, any substance that contains triglycerides in its composition can be used for the production of biodiesel. Triglycerides are found in vegetable oils and animal fats, as well as waste oils and fats. In addition to triglycerides, fatty acids are also sources for the production of biodiesel. The raw materials for obtaining biodiesel can be classified into 4 categories: oils and fats of animal origin, oils and fats of vegetable origin, frying residual oils, and sewage grease [4].

Transesterification, one of the most important processes for the production of biodiesel, is to react vegetable oil or animal fat, which are sources of triglycerides, with alcohol, in the presence of a catalyst, producing glycerol and fatty acid esters (biodiesel). Fig. 1 shows the transesterification reaction.

Fig. 1 Generic transesterification reaction [5]

III. PHASE EQUILIBRIUM

In this work, the thermodynamic model adopted for the prediction of phase equilibrium and calculation of the activity coefficient was UNIQUAC. This model proved to be the most adequate, based on the results of Lee et al. [6], in the prediction of liquid-liquid equilibrium and liquid-vapor equilibrium for the components used in the simulation. The equation of the UNIQUAC model consists of two parts: a combinatorial part, which describes the entropic contributions of the components; and a residual part, which takes into account the molecular

D. M. O. Silva is with the Superintendence of Technical-Scientific Police, Goiânia, GO, Brazil (corresponding author, phone: 55-21-999432651; e-mail: diegomos@policiacientifica.go.gov.br).

F. L. P. Pessoa is with the School of Chemistry, Federal University of Rio

de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil (e-mail: pessoa@eq.ufrj.br).

A. L. H. Costa is with the Institute of Chemistry, State University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil (e-mail: andrehc@uerj.br).

interactions responsible for the enthalpy of the mixture. The combinatorial part depends only on the composition, size and shape of the molecules, requiring only data of the pure components; while the residual part depends on the intermolecular forces, from where the adjustable parameters arise, for each pair of components (binary parameters). The expression of the UNIQUAC model is:

$$\ln \gamma_i = \ln \left(\frac{\phi_i}{x_i} \right) + 0,5q_i \ln \left(\frac{\theta_i}{\phi_i} \right) + L_i - \left(\frac{\phi_i}{x_i} \right) \sum_j L_j x_j + q_i \left(1 - \frac{\sum_j \theta_j \tau_{ji}}{\sum_k \theta_k \tau_{ki}} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$L_i = 0,5Z(r_j - q_j) - r_j + 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\theta_i = \frac{q_i}{\sum_j q_j x_j} \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = \exp - \left[\frac{a_{ij} + b_{ij}T}{RT} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_i = \frac{r_i x_i}{\sum_j r_j x_j} \quad (5)$$

$$q_i = \frac{A_{wi}}{2,5 \cdot 10^9} \quad (6)$$

$$r_i = \frac{V_{wi}}{15,17} \quad (7)$$

Z: coordination number, equal to 10; q_i : parameter of the molecular structure dependent on the size of the component; r_i : parameter of molecular structure dependent on the volume of the molecule; A_{wi} : Van der Waals area; V_{wi} : volume of Van der Waals; a_{ij} : energetic parameter of interaction between components i and j, independent of temperature [cal/gmol]; b_{ij} : energetic parameter of interaction between components i and j, dependent on temperature [cal/gmol*K].

The UNIQUAC model is applicable to a wide variety of non-electrolytic liquid mixtures containing polar or non-polar components, including partially miscible systems. This work utilized the results of Lee et al. [6] to predict the liquid-liquid balance of the ternary systems glycerol/methanol/methyl oleate and water/methanol/methyl oleate. Lee et al. concluded that the UNIQUAC model is the most adequate in predicting the experimental data of phase equilibrium of the systems studied, the binary parameters of the adjusted model are presented in Table I. There is, however, a small adaptation to Hysys in relation to the parameters as they are placed in [6]. In the article are called b_{ij} the parameters a_{ij} of Table I, in addition it is necessary to multiply them by -R (-1,98 cal/gmol*K).

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF BINARY INTERACTION OF THE UNIQUAC MODEL [6]

a_{ij} (cal/gmol)	Water	Methanol	Glycerol	Oleate
Water	-	-1536	x	-239,41
Methanol	585,01	-	-491,18	71,82
Glycerol	x	1353,07	-	63,69
Oleate	2684,12	556,86	1378,61	-

The parameters in Table I correspond to the a_{ij} of (4). The b_{ij} parameters of the equation are all null. The study of the binary interaction parameters for water/glycerol and

glycerol/water was omitted by Lee et al. [6] since they consider that such parameters do not have a significant influence on the equilibrium of the system.

For the prediction of liquid-vapor equilibrium in ethanol + esters systems and water solubility in biodiesel, although Oliveira et al. [7] state that SAFT (Statistical Association Fluid Theory) equations are the best option, Tu et al. [8] used the UNIQUAC model to satisfactorily describe liquid-vapor equilibrium data of binary mixtures of methanol with methyl esters. In addition, of course, Lee et al. [6] study also confirmed such use of the UNIQUAC model.

IV. TRANSESTERIFICATION KINETICS

The production of biodiesel by transesterification consists in reacting vegetable oil or animal fat, triglyceride source, with methanol (or ethanol), in the presence of a catalyst, producing glycerol and methyl (or ethyl) fatty acid esters - biodiesel. Alcohol is added in excess in order to shift equilibrium for maximum biodiesel yield and also to facilitate product separation by forming two partially miscible phases (one rich in glycerin and one rich in biodiesel esters).

Noureddini and Zhu [9] investigated the transesterification of soybean oil with methanol and sodium hydroxide catalyst at atmospheric pressure, varying the reaction temperature and the mixing intensity of the reaction medium, and keeping the methanol/oil ratio constant (6:1) and the catalyst content (0.2% by weight oil). According to the Noureddini and Zhu [9], the transesterification reaction is formed of three consecutive and reversible stages, corresponding to the formation of diglyceride, mono glyceride and glycerol. Each step produces one of the three methyl ester molecules of the global stoichiometry, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Partial reactions of biodiesel transesterification.

The kinetic modeling of the above reactions, of second order for all (first order in relation to each reagent), showed good adequacy to the experimental points. The parameters of the Arrhenius equation were obtained for all direct and reverse reactions, as shown in Table II. The data assume intensity of mixing of the reaction medium, equivalent to the Reynolds number equal to 6200.

Santos [10] reported some experiments involving basic homogeneous catalysis from castor, soybean and bovine tallow oils, using methanol and ethanol, as well as several catalysts, at 50 °C. From soybean oil, methanol and sodium hydroxide, the work presents conversion data of 91.5% (30 min) and 92.1% (60 min), to 0.4% by weight of catalyst; and 93.3% (30 min) and 93.5% (60 min) to 0.8% by weight of catalyst; all

considering methanol/oil molar ratio 6: 1, among others. The study concluded that the reaction time is the least influential variable in the reaction conversion, when compared to other variables such as catalyst content and molar ratio methanol/oil, also investigated in the work of Santos. In addition, a kinetic study was performed with some oil/alcohol/catalyst systems, most of which showed better adjustment of the experimental data according to the second order model; being presented the speeds found (all at 50 °C).

TABLE II
KINETIC PARAMETERS OF THE ARRHENIUS EQUATION, RE = 6200 [9]

Reaction	E_a (cal/mol)	k (L/mol*min) a 50°C	k_0 (L/mol*min)
TG → DG	13145	0.050	$3.89*10^7$
DG → TG	9932	0.110	$5.74*10^5$
DG → MG	19860	0.215	$5.82*10^{12}$
MG → DG	14639	1.228	$9.78*10^9$
MG → GL	6421	0.242	$5.33*10^3$
GL → MG	9588	0.007	$2.14*10^4$

Bessa et al. [11] reported in their work the simulation of a transesterification reactor, evaluating the influence of its volume on the conversion of the reaction with soybean oil and methanol. Conversions from 91.8% to 97.4% were found in some of the computational tests.

Due to the high conversion of the reaction, from 91.5% to 93.5%, according to Santos [10], and up to 97%, according to Bessa et al. [11], a simplification of the kinetic model was made in this work, so as to consider only the global reaction and its reverse reaction. Therefore, the kinetic parameters chosen in the reaction model were those referring to the last partial reaction (direct and reverse), given in the last two lines of Table II. The choice of this reaction, to the detriment of the slower reaction of the set of partial reactions, was due to all reactions having velocities of the same order of magnitude. It is common practice to use the latter partial reaction as representative of the kinetics, as it results in the formation of the major compounds of transesterification (biodiesel and glycerol). Thus, the kinetic parameters considered in the simulations were: 6421 cal/mol and 9588 cal/mol, for the energies of activation of the direct and reverse reactions, respectively; and $5,33*10^3$ L/(mol*min) and $2,14*10^4$ L/(mol*min) for the pre-exponential constants of the forward and reverse reactions, respectively.

V. STOCHASTIC SIMULATION GENERATION METHODOLOGY

Having the simulation of mean values in hand, the next step was to choose the output variable that would be evaluated, and for that, which input variables would be disturbed. After choosing the variable in question that would be disturbed, and already knowing its average value that was adopted in the Hysys simulation and a certain standard deviation that was adopted for such variable, a normal distribution was then performed in Excel. In this distribution 100 different values were generated for the variable at the process input, which was disturbed. In order to communicate the Excel spreadsheet that contained the values with the Hysys simulation, a VBA simulation environment was created in which the input data were exported to the simulation in Hysys and retrieved back the output data of the variable being evaluated. These data were

then sent back to the Excel worksheet where the histograms were processed and later generated.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The oil chosen as source of raw material for the biodiesel represented in the simulation was soybean oil. This choice was made based on the large supply of this oil in the country. In addition, biodiesel was chosen from a transesterification methyl route, so the currents in the simulation after the reaction stage contain not only the ester (biodiesel), but methanol that is used in excess in the reaction, triglycerides (soybean oil), and glycerin which is by-product of the reaction, in addition to water participating in the process in the washing step. Another hypothesis taken at this stage was the consideration of soybean oil to be formed only by triglycerides, thus disregarding the diacylglycerides and monoglycerides, for simplification purposes. The thermodynamic model adopted was UNIQUAC. Also, it was not considered in this simulation the adoption of an electrolyte model, due to the possibility of occurrence of saponification reaction of the triglyceride in the presence of basic catalysis, such situation was not raised in this study. In this simulation with the presence of only one ester in the process input stream, inserted in Hysys, the triglyceride triolein was chosen as the raw material for soybean oil. This is because the methyl oleate ester is the one that is present in higher concentration in biodiesel formed from soybean oil and methanol.

TABLE III
MASS COMPOSITION OF SAMPLE ESTERS OF BIODIESEL BASED ON SOYBEAN AND METHANOL [12]

Ester	Soybean M
Laurate	0.0006
Myristate	0.1110
Palmitate	0.0006
Palmitoleate	0.0283
Stearate	0.2374
Oleate	0.5556
Linoleate	0.0553
Linolenate	0.0028
Arachidonate	0.0017
Gadoleate	0.0032
Behenate	0.0006
Erucate	0.0015
Lignocerate	0.0013
Total Composition	1.0000

As can be seen in Table III, oleate represents 55.56% in biodiesel from soybean and methanol. The choice of only one ester to represent biodiesel was based on previous work by Bessa et al. [11] and Lim et al. [13]. Moreover, there was a greater abundance of phase equilibrium data in the literature for methyl oleate/water/methanol and methyl oleate/glycerol/methanol ternary than for the other esters constituting biodiesel, in addition to the kinetic data of the reaction with triolein.

A. Base Case Simulation

The plant used for simulation was based on the proposal of the company Lurgi [14], which used vacuum purification

processes of biodiesel and on the biodiesel plant project for the Aranda and Cruz [15] methyl route. The simulated plant has a production capacity of approximately 957 kg/h of biodiesel and uses for this purpose a mass flow of soybean oil and methanol, respectively, of 1000 kg/h and 214 kg/h, respecting the molar ratio (6:1) of methanol/soybean oil according to Santos [10]. From a practical point of view, it can be considered that the plant capacity would correspond to a pilot scale project. The process flow diagram of the unit is shown in Fig. 3. The inlet current of the CSTR-100 reactor has ambient temperature, but follows with a pressure of 130 kPa in order to avoid vaporization of part of the reaction mixture inside the reactor, since the transesterification reaction of the biodiesel is exothermic and therefore the temperature increases much in the course of the reaction. In addition, the temperature of the step is controlled so as to maintain it at about 50 °C. The reactor output current then proceeds to a settling stage where the phases rich in glycerin (heavy3 stream) and biodiesel (light3 stream) are separated. The currents called dummy, in the process, have zero flow. They are necessary because the simulator asks them to be placed due to the possibility of vaporization of part of the load.

According to Lee et al. [6], methanol is preferentially distributed in the aqueous phase when compared to the biodiesel rich phase. This fact suggests that an initial purification of the biodiesel can be made relatively easily by washing with water. To the stream "light3" is mixed with a stream of wash water in the mixer MIX-102, the outlet stream 4 then follows into a wash tank. In this separation unit (extractor V-101) the washed biodiesel exits stream 4_1, while the washing water containing methanol and glycerol exits from the bottom in stream 4_2. The glycerin-rich stream, but also having unreacted methanol and triolein in its composition, is mixed with the stream 4_2 in the MIX-100 mixer, from which the outlet stream 6 follows into the separation vessel V-104. Such a separating vessel generates two streams, one containing glycerol impure containing about 51% by mass, and the other top containing water and methanol (stream 7). Stream 7 follows to distillation column T-100, which is intended to recycle unreacted methanol and water used in the previous wash. Processing of the washed biodiesel-containing stream (4_1) is carried out in a vacuum, associated with a reduction of the pressure in the stream from 101.3 kPa to 3.3 kPa. The purpose of this operation is to carry out purification of the biodiesel under vacuum, since the temperatures in the two flash vessels used for the refining cannot be higher than 240 °C, which is the biodiesel degradation temperature. The first vessel (V-102) has the function of removing excess water and methanol from the top (stream 5) in the wet biodiesel stream. The bottom stream containing the dried biodiesel goes to the second vessel (V-103), which aims to remove the unreacted oil content (triolein) still present in the biodiesel. The top stream of vessel V-103 possesses refined biodiesel at a mass concentration of 99.9%. According to the simulation, the other concentrations and conditions of the product stream in the base case are in accordance with ANP standards. The yield of the reaction step in this base case simulation was 96.6%, and the recovery of

biodiesel produced was 98.6%.

B. Evaluation of the Influence of Disturbances on the Pressure of the Vacuum System

The mean value used in the simulation of the base case for the "bio úmido" stream pressure was 3.3 kPa, so a standard deviation of 10% of this value was adopted to generate the normal distribution, with which the current "bio úmido" was disturbed in its variable pressure. From the successive perturbations in the pressure of the "bio úmido" stream, different final compositions were also obtained for refined biodiesel. Stochastic analysis of the pressure perturbation in the inlet stream, of the V-102 flash vessel showed that the main variable attained was the final water composition. Thus, 100 simulations were made to evaluate this influence, of the pressure perturbation in that current, in the water content of the final stream. The result was that about 85% of the simulations presented results within the specifications regarding the maximum water content allowed in biodiesel, 0.00025 (mass fraction). Therefore, the stochastic analysis, determined a probability of 15% of the proposed conditions, did not meet the specifications. Thus, according to the uncertainty allowed for the vacuum system, the stochastic simulation shows that the plant does not have an adequate degree of reliability. As a consequence, it is necessary to reset a new set-point value to increase the appropriate safety margin. It should be noted that it was considered as adequate levels of reliability, probabilities less than or equal to 10%. In order to correct the identified problem, it was attempted to reduce the set point of the pressure to obtain a range of values for the water fraction in the refined biodiesel stream, with a range acceptable from a non-specification probabilistic point of view. In practice, this reduction in the operating pressure of the vacuum system output means that a higher water content will be able to be eliminated by the V-102 flash vessel. For this purpose, the pressure set in the "wet biodiesel" current has been reduced in 10%. Maintained the previous standard deviation of 0.33 kPa, a new normal distribution of values was generated. The stochastic analysis of the perturbation at the wet-biodiesel stream pressure setpoint, now reduced to 3.0 kPa, generated a result in which about 99% of the simulations showed results within the specifications for the maximum water allowed in biodiesel, 0.00025 (mass fraction). Therefore, we found a probability that only 1% of the proposed conditions did not meet the specifications. In this context, it is possible to consider that, according to this new process specification, the plant will be able to operate reliably.

C. Influence of Disturbances on the Methanol/Oil Ratio of the Reactants, Isolated Change in the Methanol Flow Rate

The yield of the reaction step is extremely connected to the methanol/oil molar ratio, which should be 6:1, according to Santos [10]. Therefore, oscillations in the molar flow of the reactants may compromise such yield in the reactor. Based on this aspect, the stochastic analysis of this topic intends to evaluate the influence of perturbations in this proportion of methanol/oil on the yield of the reaction. For that, the methanol

flow rate was chosen as a variable that would be disturbed. Aranda and Cruz [15] assumed a yield of 95% for the projected plant, therefore such value was adopted as specification for the operation in the reactor.

As the recycle methanol streams, 99.8% methanol base concentration, and recycle water, 99.4% water base concentration, were high purity, it was considered as simplification in the stochastic simulation that the methanol stream that feeds the reactor is pure. Such a consideration was made due to the fact that when the methanol flow rate at the reactor inlet is disturbed this alters the specification of the distillation column. This change is caused since the methanol distillate rate that the column is recovering is coupled to the methanol flow rate entering the respective column. Therefore, variations in this flow also require that the column

specifications be adapted. However, as the simulation of the base case was kept fixed in its adopted variables and parameters, disturbing only the variables and parameters that were being analyzed in each specific case, it was considered for the stochastic analysis a simulation with the open recycle streams, that is, considering that the methanol stream fed to the reactor is pure. The change in this consideration implies that the simulation of the base case does not converge when the methanol stream begins to be disturbed, since if the unreacted methanol flow entering the column is different from the distillate rate to which it is associated the result is the non-convergence of this column. The oil flow rate in the base case simulation was 1.129 kmol/h, and the methanol flow rate was approximately 6.677 kmol/h, close to the 6:1 molar ratio.

Fig. 3 Flowchart of the base case simulation, obtained in Hysys.

For the stochastic analysis, now for the perturbation in methanol flow rate at the entrance of the reactor, it was observed that about 77% of the simulated flow rate showed results within the specifications with regard to the minimum efficiency considered, 95%. Therefore, the probability of 23% of the proposed conditions did not meet the specifications. Assuming such behavior is not acceptable, it is necessary to consider the modification of the methanol flow maintenance system in the reactor. For the operational correction, the objective is to reduce the probability of the conditions not meeting the specification, while maintaining the set-point of the methanol flow. For this, the standard deviation was reduced from 10% to 5% of the average flow, that is, approximately 0.334 kmol/h. Once again, stochastic analysis, now for a smaller disturbance interval generated by the reduction of the standard deviation, it can be observed that 94% of the simulated flow range presents the reaction yield results above 95%. In other words, the analysis concludes that the probability of violating the specification was reduced to 6%. Assuming this value as acceptable, it can be concluded that a standard deviation of up to 5% in the methanol flow rate at the reactor inlet would be acceptable according to the desired yield.

D. Influence of Disturbances on the Methanol/Oil Ratio of the Reactants, Change in the Methanol and Oil Flow Rates

In this case the objective remains to disturb the molar ratio methanol/oil, but the normal distribution for the lottery of the variables will not only occur in the methanol flow, but together with the perturbation of the flow of soybean oil. Based on the standard deviation of 10% of the set-point of each of the variables used in this analysis, we have for the perturbation in the methanol stream flow, which in the simulation of the base case was 6.677 kmol/h, a standard deviation of 0.668 kmol/h and for the perturbation in the flow of oil, which in the simulation of the base case was 1.129 kmol/h, a standard deviation of 0.113 kmol/h. In this way, the normal distribution was performed for both variables, taking a randomized pair and introducing them in the simulation to obtain the reaction yield. The stochastic analysis of the simultaneous perturbations in the oil and methanol flow showed that 78% of the simulations showed a reaction yield above 95%, therefore there is a 22% probability of the range of values used for the reagents not to meet the specifications of the reactor yield. In this case, the same problem of low performance is verified in a considerable number of simulations, demanding an intervention in the

system. As a correction of the situation shown in this topic, once again the standard deviation was reduced to 5% of the set-point of the flows, that is, 0.334 kmol/h for the normal distribution of the methanol flow and 0.057 kmol/h for the oil flow normal distribution. As result, it was observed in the stochastic analysis that adopting a smaller standard deviation for the distributions, the simultaneous perturbations in the oil and methanol flow rates showed that 90% of the simulations had a reaction yield above 95%, with only 10% probability of the proposed conditions do not meet the specifications for reaction yield.

VII. CONCLUSION

It is reckless in a project, the construction of a mathematical model for the accomplishment of a computational simulation without taking into account the uncertainties in the parameters. In this scenario, the proposal of this work is based on the presentation of several case studies associated to the uncertainty management, using stochastic simulation tools, in the analysis of a biodiesel production plant. In this evaluation, we considered the variables that, when disturbed, could change the results of operations. In the biodiesel purification stage, the vacuum system has considerable influence on the final composition of the product. Depending on the pressure value, the water content in the final product was affected, obeying or not the maximum limit allowed by the ANP. In the stochastic analysis of the pressure in this stage of biodiesel purification, a probability of 15% of the proposed conditions did not meet the specifications, concluding, therefore, that this number was quite high. As an alternative to improve this result, it was decided to decrease the value of the pressure being used in the set-point, from 3.3 kPa to 3.0 kPa, maintaining the same standard deviation used previously. Since, under a lower pressure, and keeping operating temperatures in the V-102 and V-103 flash vessels constant, water would be evaporated more efficiently. As a result, there was a drop to about 1% probability that the conditions did not meet the specification for the maximum water content in biodiesel.

As for the production stage of biodiesel, one of the factors of greatest influence on the yield of the reaction is the methanol/oil ratio of the reactants. In this topic of study, perturbations were made in the molar ratio of the reagents, which by the literature should be 6:1. At first, the flow of methanol was disturbed in isolation. In the corresponding stochastic simulation, the set-point adopted for the methanol flow rate was 6.677 kmol/h, with a standard deviation of 10% of that value, or 0.688 kmol/h. As a result, it was found that 23% of the proposed conditions presented results outside the specification adopted for the yield of the reaction. Subsequently, in order to reduce this risk of failure, it was decided to shorten the normal distribution range that was being used in the simulation. Therefore, the set-point was maintained, but now the standard deviation was reduced to 0.344 kmol/h, and as a result a 6% probability of the conditions breached the yield specification.

Continuing the analysis of the influence of changes in the methanol/oil ratio, simultaneous perturbations were also made in the oil and methanol flow rates. Through the joint draw for

the two variables, by the normal distribution, the values obtained for the oil flow, set-point 1.129 kmol/h, with a standard deviation of 0.113 kmol/h and for the methanol flow, set-point 6.677 kmol/h, with a standard deviation of 0.668 kmol/h were introduced in the simulator, obtaining as a response of this stochastic analysis 22% probability of the simulated conditions did not meet the specification of the yield. Again, reducing the flow rates used in the simulations, by reducing the standard deviations of the studied variables, i.e. to 5% of the respective set points, a new result was achieved, with only 10% of probability of new conditions escaping the specification. Given the aforementioned facts, it can be affirmed that one of the benefits of probabilistic versus deterministic simulation was proven in this work, which is, precisely, to know the probability value of a given response and, therefore, if that result is unreliable or not, and if it is possible to determine more clearly the safety margins that must be introduced in a project.

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